

ORGANIZATION OF TURKIC STATES AND DIASPORA COORDINATION**Babanli Yahya**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15960850>**Abstract**

The time of global change opens up new opportunities for the introduction and dissemination of breakthrough technologies, connecting the potential of developed and developing countries. In this regard, international integration is becoming one of the main trends in the development of the modern world. It is the civilizational proximity of the integrating countries that provides the foundation and stability of this association. Historical ties, common goals and objectives, and the similarity of the problems of the Turkic-speaking countries are one of the important factors that united the Turkic peoples. A prerequisite for regional integration is the desire to integrate all Turkic peoples into a single space, and most importantly, to ensure that the interests of the Turkic peoples are adequately represented in this association, including through consolidated advocacy of the interests of the Turkic peoples.

In the field of international relations, the diaspora, as a part of public diplomacy, has become important, becoming a kind of entity. The current difficult geopolitical and economic situation forces different states to pursue a more active policy with the diaspora. In order to integrate the diasporas of the Turkic-speaking countries and assess the possibilities of cooperation between them at different levels, work is underway. Taking into account the variety of existing problems in the activities of diasporas of Turkic-speaking countries, a common strategy was developed to adequately respond to various situations.

Keywords: Organization of Turkic States, diaspora, Turkic peoples, The Turkic Council, joint action

Introduction

The transformation of the unipolar model of the world into a multipolar one has become a defining modern trend. The time of global change opens up new opportunities for the introduction and dissemination of breakthrough technologies, connecting the potential of developed and developing countries. In this regard, international integration is becoming one of the main trends in the development of the modern world. At the same time, various forms of integration of countries can be sustainable if they rely on both economic and powerful civilizational factors [5, p.77-79]. It is the civilizational proximity of the integrating countries that provides the foundation and stability of this association. The creation of an integration union of Turkic states is one of the geopolitical scenarios. Historical ties, common goals and objectives, and the similarity of the problems of the Turkic-speaking countries are one of the important factors that united the Turkic peoples. A prerequisite for regional integration is the desire to integrate all Turkic peoples into a single space, and most importantly, to ensure that the interests of the Turkic peoples are adequately represented in this association, including through consolidated advocacy of the interests of the Turkic peoples.

In the field of international relations, the diaspora, as a part of public diplomacy, has become important, becoming a kind of entity. The current difficult geopolitical and economic situation forces different states to pursue the most active policy in relations with the diaspora. Turkiye has also not remained indifferent to such a policy. Against the background of the economic, political and ideological changes that took place in the country after the Justice and Development Party came to power, the role of the Turkish diaspora as a "soft power" promoting public diplomacy was also empha-

sized. On the one hand, a policy of establishing and developing stable relations with the diaspora was pursued, on the other hand, by strengthening these ties, the foundations of the process of capitalizing on the political, economic, and scientific potential of the diaspora were laid.

In the format of state-Diaspora cooperation, the issue of cooperation with diasporas of other countries was also included in the agenda as a separate area of foreign policy. First of all, it had to be carried out with diasporas of Turkic-speaking peoples, then with diasporas of strategic interest to Turkiye. At first, cooperation was limited to the Turkish-Azerbaijani tandem, and at the preliminary stage, the emphasis was mainly on the organizational (structural) work of the diaspora, since the community institutions of both countries lack a strategy.

They carried out weak activities, moreover, the vast majority of them were marginalized, did not have great financial opportunities and did not represent a serious political force. Taking into account the variety of existing problems, steps have been developed to address them, as well as a common strategy governing the activities of the diasporas of the two countries, which have undergone certain changes in order to adequately respond to crises and face various challenges.

Initiatives to mobilize diasporas of Turkic States

By the end of the 20th century, geopolitical changes had determined Turkiye's leading role in the "Turkic world." Former Turkish President Turgut Ozal called the 21st century the "century of Turkiye," while Prime Minister Suleiman Demirel spoke about Turkiye's leadership capabilities "from the Adriatic coast to the Great Wall of China," the role of a "historical Magnet," a "cultural center" for emerging Turkish states. [4, p. 76]. At the state level, regular sum-

mits of Turkic states have become one of the mechanisms for developing and strengthening ties between Türkiye and the republics of the Caucasus and Central Asia: by the end of the first decade of the 21st century, nine such summits had been held. According to Turkish President Ahmet Gul, these summits are a platform for solidarity and exchange of views on both issues of relations between the Turkic countries and global issues.

The policy of rapprochement and joint activities of the Turkic-speaking states is partly implemented within the framework of the activities of the "Turkic Council" established under the Nakhichevan Treaty (2009), of which Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan are members. Since its establishment, the Council has taken political, economic (including customs), scientific, cultural and tourism spheres as the basis for cooperation between the Turkic-speaking states, and has also taken active steps to establish and strengthen ties between the diasporas of the member States [8, p.144-145].

Projects aimed at implementing global tasks were included in the political agenda, new models and areas of cooperation were put forward, which, in fact, formed part of the policy of "diaspora building". It should be noted that state and non-state management bodies were involved in the search for mechanisms for mutual cooperation, which form both a single agenda (sectoral cooperation) and outline a roadmap for actions related to a particular area.

In 2013, at a meeting of the heads of departmental structures responsible for Diaspora affairs of the member countries of the "Turkic Council" (Baku), a "Contact Group of Responsible Persons for Diaspora Affairs" was established, the functions and practical steps of which with the diasporas of the member countries were fixed in the document "Strategy of joint activities of Diasporas of Turkic-speaking countries" [6, p.117].

In order to enhance the participation of diasporas of the Turksoy member countries in the political and economic life of their countries of residence, the council focused its work on such topical issues as consolidating economic potential and strengthening ties between entrepreneurs, as well as actions aimed at shaping the image of their countries or the Turkic world through various events and information policy. The Council also seeks to create an influential lobby, and it is no coincidence that the structures on diaspora issues and responsible state bodies of its member states have put forward possible options towards achieving strategic goals, one of which was the creation of an organization that not only connects diasporic communities of Turkic-speaking states, but also coordinates their work [7, 115–137]. Based on these considerations, it was decided to create regional diaspora centers with the participation of organizations and delegates from the diasporas of the four countries. The first such center started operating in Kiev in 2014, the central office of which is located in the building of the Union of Azerbaijanis of Ukraine. This policy has also found a place in the activities of the Office of Turks Living Abroad and Friendly Societies, established in 2010 and operating under the Government of Türkiye, which, in addition to

solving and coordinating the problems of Turkish communities, also aimed to counter the slanderous propaganda of the Armenian lobby.

It should be noted that Armenian news portals, such as "Diario Armenia", focus on more news about Azerbaijan and Türkiye in order to denigrate their identity in the world community. On January 15, the "LaTecla info" website also published an article about the Second Karabakh War written by Eugenio Zaffaroni, an Argentine lawyer and judge of the Inter-American Court of Human Rights, who is one of the closest figures in the Diaspora, where Azerbaijan is accused of continuing the so-called "genocide of 1915" jointly with Türkiye [4, 2021, p. 8].

An analysis of the intentions of the Armenian Diaspora in Latin America shows that this is an open attack on two members of the Organization of Turkic-speaking States. It is obvious that the forces are deliberately uniting against Türkiye and Azerbaijan, and the action is being organized. This is clearly seen in the activities of the Armenian Diaspora in Cyprus. As the Armenian National Committee of Cyprus (AS Cyprus) has asked the city committee to change the name of the street named after Talat Pasha in Paphos, Cyprus. The organization's representatives justified this by saying that Talat Pasha was the so-called "organizer of the Armenian Genocide." Subsequently, the name of the street was changed to "Dikayosine" by decision of the mayor and the city council. [4, 2021, p. 6].

Commenting on Ankara's position in a letter from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs to Washington, diplomat Ibrahim Kalin noted that normalization of relations with Armenia would undoubtedly make life easier for Armenians in Türkiye. Relations with Armenia will make a significant contribution to other areas, but the Armenian diaspora, which is concentrated here, and the countries of the world must also act responsibly. According to I. Kalin, Armenian lobbyists and political circles opposed to Türkiye intend to sow new claims and seeds of hostility, falsifying historical realities. The Turkish state and people will not accept this lie and deceitful campaign [3].

Measures to form a common diaspora

Traditionally, diaspora cooperation includes itself the meetings and minutes of the Azerbaijan- Türkiye High Level Strategic Cooperation Council. In our view, the "Joint Action Strategy of Azerbaijani and Turkish Diaspora Organizations" based on the Consent Protocol signed at the joint conference of Azerbaijani and Turkish diaspora organizations held in Antalya, Türkiye, on June 7, 2006 is a preliminary example and represents the beginning of a new era for Turkish world diasporas.

If we pay attention to the report on the tripartite political consultations held on May 4, 2018 in Baku at the level of deputy foreign ministers of Azerbaijan-Ukraine-Türkiye, we can see that the diaspora inter-agency cooperation is promising. This document outlines the importance of implementing cultural and humanitarian projects that will strongly enhance cooperation between states and serve to bring about convergence among nations. As a continuation of this activity,

the Azerbaijani, Ukrainian and Turkish diaspora organizations operating abroad are shown to ensure the coordinated activities.

The joint action strategy of Azerbaijani and Turkish diaspora organizations is in accordance with its objective, based on the strategic partnership relations between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Türkiye, to deepen cooperation in the field of diaspora construction, to bring information about the history, modern life, socio-economic development level, culture of both nations to the global community, to guide their capabilities towards a unified goal of improving the efficiency of the activities of diaspora organizations, to increase the opportunities for participation in socio-political processes in countries inhabited by Azerbaijanis and Turkish residing in foreign countries, as well as to promote relations between all Turkic peoples.

The development of mutually beneficial cooperation in lobby building, the exchange of experiences, the identification of problems present in the protection of rights and freedoms of Azerbaijanis and Turks living in foreign countries, and the preparation of proposals to eliminate them and the list of Azerbaijani and Turkish students studying at prestigious higher educational institutions of the world, led to the establishment of contacts. In this particular case, efforts have been booming in recent years. New formats of collaboration and partnership are emerging. The multiplicity of collaborative events with different profiles is appreciated.

The First Baku Forum of Diaspora Youth of Turkic States was organized by the State Committee on Work with Diaspora of the Republic of Azerbaijan and in partnership with the Organization of Turkic States. The members of delegations from Turkmenistan, the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus and Hungary with the status of observer, along with Azerbaijan, Türkiye, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, attend the event.

On October 14, 2024, the 1st International Turkish Diaspora in Türkiye's Century" Symposium was organized in Erzincan city. Turkish Vice President Cevdet Yilmaz sent a congratulatory message to the participants of the symposium. According to the politician, each of the more than 7 million Turkish citizens living abroad is representative not only of their homeland, but also of the entire Turkic world. In his message, he urged his compatriots to protect national identity and not sever ties with Türkiye. He noted that "the non-governmental organizations of the Turkish diaspora play pivotal role in coping with Islamophobia and xenophobia abroad, especially in Western countries." Cevdet Yilmaz expressed confidence that Turkish state authorities are ready to protect the rights and interests of Turkish citizens abroad, including their education in native language. It is known that the ministers and diaspora bodies of the OTS cooperate. Meetings, events are even held on a regular basis.

On November 18, 2024, the 16th meeting of the Committee on Interethnic Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries under the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan was organized in Tashkent. The event had brought together the representative

of the Secretary-General of the TDI, the Deputy Chairman of the State Committee on Work with Diaspora of Azerbaijan, the President of the Otandastar Foundation of Kazakhstan, the President of Turks Abroad and Related Communities, the Chairman of the Committee on Interethnic Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries of Uzbekistan, and the Deputy Minister of Labor, Social Protection and Migration of Kyrgyzstan.

During the meeting, the parties focused on efforts to improve cooperation and coordination with diasporas, increasing the effectiveness and diaspora capacity of the exchange of experience programs among the relevant government agencies, as well as the organization of the Turkic Diaspora Forum, which will be held with the participation of young people, as well as the broader participation of Turkic diaspora representatives in the youth, economic and academic initiatives of TDT.

At the meeting, the SCO agreed to conduct the 2nd Internship Programme for representatives of the agencies responsible for the work on diaspora of the OTS Member States in Azerbaijan in 2025, and the 3rd Potential Training Programme for Turkic-speaking Diasporas in the Czech Republic."

It is these steps that serve to deepen strategic cooperation in the diasporal sphere in the context of a new world order that creates a basis for communities to work together domestically, as well as internationally, and enhances congenies.

Meetings like these open up promising opportunities and diasporas make the relationship a reason for the purposeful development of national issues in the future.

The most progressive approach and method for determining a long-term goal is the elimination of the act that determines the Turkic origin held by the Turkish state. That is, the issuance of a "Document confirming Turk origin" for exemptions to Turkic nationals. From the Embassy of the State of which the person is a citizen, the affirmative statement that he/she is a "Turk" becomes evidence that makes it easier for him/her to live and work in the Republic of Türkiye.

One of the specific areas of increasingly multidisciplinary political cooperation is the strengthening of cooperation among diasporas. Improving the image of member countries internationally and conducting investigations to have an impact on public opinion in the areas where Turkic states and peoples live are among the main objectives of the Organization of Turkic States.

For instance, "On the initiative of the country's President Ilham Aliyev undertaken at the Friendship, Brotherhood and Cooperation Congress of Turkic-speaking States and Communities (TUDEV) in Antalya in September 2006, the First Forum of Heads of Azerbaijani and Turkish Diaspora Organizations was held in Baku on March 9, 2007, and on June 21, 2013, I Forum of the Leaders of Diaspor Organizations of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States. In addition to representatives of the diaspora, representatives of state and government structures, non-governmental organizations, science, culture and other creative institutions of the republics of Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Türkiye participated in the Forum [2, p. 42].

Representatives of Azerbaijan, Türkiye, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan participated in the First Capacity Building Training Program of Turkic-speaking Diasporas, organized jointly by the Turkish Council and the Turks Abroad and Related Communities.

These steps may be considered important for the formation of the common diaspora. Meetings and Diaspora Forums are held regularly at the level of Contact Groups, as well as with ministers and heads of organizations responsible for the work of the diaspora, to discuss the scale and nature of cooperation among OTS diaspora.

The Eight Istanbul Summit of Turkic Council, held on 12 November 2021, changed its name to the Organization of Turkic States and adopted a fairly comprehensive strategic document "Turkic World Vision-2040". On November 12, 2022, the adoption of the "Samarkand Declaration" at the 9th Summit of the Organization of the Turkic States was considered to clarify the steps that will be taken towards the realization of the organization's vision of 2040. Türkiye's rapprochement with the Islamic world is assessed through the prism of expanding the geostrategic horizons of a country that in the past was obsessed with following an exclusively Western trajectory. [9, p. 132].

They encourage ministers and heads of agencies responsible for the diaspora affairs of the OTS to increase coordination and cooperation within the framework of the Turkic World Vision 2040, which includes the Joint Action Strategy of the Turkic-speaking Diaspora, the annual "Joint Action Plans of the Turkic Diaspora", the "OTS 2022-2026 Strategy", as well as the "Turkic World Vision 2040", which was held at the Astana Summit of the OTS on November 3, 2023, and was signed in Azerbaijani, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkish and Uzbek languages.

"Turkic World Vision 2040" included priority issues such as "Developing a framework for diaspora involvement and investment in the countries of origin; mobilizing academic diaspora to support higher education and scientific institutions in the Turkic world and strengthening relationships among scientists from diaspora around the world; and ensuring the active participation of Turkish diaspora communities in relevant projects and programs of the Organization of Turkic States."

Yes, "Complementing the organizing process with specific achievements, the Organization of Turkic States is moving forward to a new era in which it aims to further deepen cooperation with the "Turkic World-2040" vision. The organization is a symbol of the shared power of the Turkic world and a product of unshakable solidarity."

The OTS states adopted "The Return of Kazakhs Abroad to Motherland-Kazakhstan - Oralman" and "State Programs Abroad for 2005-2007, as well as" The Law of the Republic of Kyrgyzstan, which provides state support for ethnic Kyrgyzstan returning to the historic homeland " [1, 234 p.]

Based on the neighboring Kazakhstan's experience, Kyrgyzstan developed a program "Kayrilman" aimed at the return of Kyrgyz people living abroad to the country and granting them citizenship, taking into

account that this process will facilitate demographic boom, as well as overcome the problem of shortage of specialists. The main goal of the Kayrilman program is to create a wide range of opportunities for Kyrgyz people living abroad and to obtain various benefits in the country. For the purpose of the implementation of the Program, the Laws on Citizenship and Foreign Migration have been amended and made additions.

It can be used to take advantage of this experience and achieve goals.

Prospective opportunities

Turkish investigative correspondent Abdullah Bozkurt gives important details about Türkiye's connection to the diaspora in his article titled "Türkiye expands diaspora ties to promote political objectives abroad" on the Nordic Monitor website. The article states, "The Turkish Government plans to strengthen its support for diaspora groups abroad, both financially and through other means, in order to promote stronger loyalty to Türkiye, address legal and administrative difficulties in host countries, promote active political engagement, and build relationships with NGOs."

Among the interesting facts, the Turkish Government's diaspora agency, the Presidency for Turks Abroad and Related Communities (YTB), has prepared a 71-page official report titled "Strategic Plan 2024-2028". The agency's vision, mission, and strategy is to mobilize nearly seven million members of the diaspora community to advance the policies of the Turkish Government. YTB stated that students of the Turkic diaspora who receive a scholarship from the government to study in Türkiye will be "voluntary Turkish ambassadors". YTB also suggested contacting "Turkish companies engaged in foreign trade" in order for these students to become "economic actors" in the countries where they live. The YTB also cooperates with non-Turkic groups, called "cohabiting communities," which include global Islamist networks such as the Muslim Brotherhood and Hizb-ut-Tahrir."

YTB closely monitors the activities of 15,000 foreign exchange students studying on government scholarship from 170 countries. During a speech on May 6, Erdogan announced that there were 340,000 foreign students from 198 countries. "In addition, the agency (YTB) coordinates educational activities with more than 150,000 graduates who have completed their education in Türkiye. Erdogan's Government also funds and supports NGOs to complete YTB activities with a budget of \$92.5 million. One of the main beneficiaries of this program is the UID, which is the key support for the President Erdogan."

The adoption of the Declaration "Combating Islamophobia and Turkophobia" at the conclusion of the First International Symposium of Turkish Diaspora, held in the framework of the "Turkish Century" in Erzinan, Türkiye, with the participation of representatives of up to 300 Turkic diasporas from 33 countries of the world and officials of the OTS Member States, is a remarkable case for the future. Indeed, such measures contribute to the expansion of mutual activity among diaspora organizations and to the strengthening of international positions of countries, the OTS and the Turkish diaspora.

Outcomes and savings.

In general, these three aspects should be approached carefully:

- Principle participation in the development of global processes.
- Provide information control, advisory service.
- Monitoring the situation and reviewing the execution of the strategy.

The coordination of diasporas' activities is important because of the similarity of historical experience and the specifics of geography. The diaspora, among the main actors of the contemporary world, must make the most effective use of the factor. The OTS "Diaspora Hub" should be established and transitioned to digital diaspora activity. Internet resources should be widely used and collaborative platforms should be realized on social networking accounts.

It is known that along with Azerbaijani Houses, Turkish Houses and Yunus Emre Institute are functioning in different countries of the world. For the benefit of the general work, it would be advisable to use this potential for the use of OTS members and other Turkic peoples, as well as friendly nations. In addition, in order to better promote and teach Turkic culture, history, language and literature, along with its people, various activities are carried out by these institutions, researches are made to support scientific work in collaboration with different organizations, and to convene the results to the wide public through their publication in various newspapers and magazines.

In 2021, R.T. Erdogan said that the new Turkish House will have the permanent representation of Türkiye at the United Nations, the consulate in New York, and the permanent representation of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, which will host political, economic, and cultural events: "Our new Turkish House will serve our citizens, compatriots, relatives, and friendly communities living in the United States. I believe that the Turkish House, which will be one of New York's landmark buildings, will be ready to serve Türkiye-U.S. relations and UN Member States." It seems that at the present time when the world is on the threshold of a new plain, there has been a good opportunity for the joint action of Turkic states, and it has become a great necessity for each of them in terms of their national interests. The case with the diaspora is also of this invoice. Mathematical and statistical calculations also show that cooperation in this field is on the rise. It is confined to all spheres of states and societies.

In 2023, "5 State 1 Diaspora with the Organization of Turkic States" sessions were organized as part of the opening ceremony of the Tenth Congress of the World Turkic Business Council (ODI) in Istanbul. Discussions were held and questions answered on the possibility of expanding economic cooperation within the framework of OTS. The event, which was attended by officials of the Member States of the Organization of Turkic States, representatives of business circles and international organizations, the issues of economic cooperation, the expansion of partnerships between diaspora organizations of the Member States, and joint investment opportunities were discussed. The issues of

supporting innovative, small and medium-sized businesses, youth, women and businesses from the diaspora were also discussed. Furthermore, it would be advisable for intellectual institutions to undertake the following apprenticeships:

- Establishing OTS internal coordination, identifying action perspectives in line with calls to action in order to make cooperation important;
- Developing diaspora joint activity platforms and signing of memorandums of understanding in non-OTS countries;
- Implementing academic projects on diasporas and expansion of relations among scientists across countries;
- Establishing relationships among students studying in foreign countries;
- Establishing coordinating boards, intercontinental networks, and organizations internationally across countries;
- Arranging formats in parallel with media outlets and representatives;
- Reviewing the proposal regarding Common Turk House project and establishing the World Turkish Diaspora Day in order to live and spread its culture and traditions;
- Realizing cultural mass events (festivals, concerts, decades, etc.), etc.

The resurgence factor of the diaspora of Turkic peoples is the same. With all particulars in mind, organizations of Turkic States (OTS) should take an asymmetric approach to work with the diaspora at the level and develop a strategic roadmap on the importance of cooperation and prospects for action.

Effective work requires combined diaspora engineering. This should be in the context of social relations and as a social identity perspective. In fact, diaspora organizations should be a bridge between the two countries, promote the development of all directions of relations, use the auxiliary potential of public diplomacy to positively influence the overall dynamics of relations. The characteristics of the formation of the diaspora of Turkic states should be analyzed, problems studied, organizational design and strategy developed.

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